

MAGNETISM AND CATALYSIS. PART II. CATALYSIS OF PERSULPHATE AND IODIDE REACTION BY FERROUS IONS.

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Magnetic evidence is adduced in regard to the formation of a relatively stable intermediate compound which is responsible for the accelerated velocity of the iodide-persulphate reaction. The reaction obviously does not take place merely *via* the formation of ferric sulphate which has been the view so far. The nature of the compound is discussed.

Recently the mechanism of the catalytic reaction between persulphate and iodide has elicited some controversy. Calculations based on the measurements of reaction velocity in the presence of Fe^{++} ions led Kiss and Zombory (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 225) to express the reaction as follows:—

Saai (*ibid.*, 1928, **47**, 385), while studying the velocity of ionic reactions observed that the amount of iodine formed by catalysis, as calculated from the coefficient of these reactions, is not compatible with the observed value and hence concluded that the catalytic influence cannot be wholly explained by these reactions. Kiss (*ibid.*, 1929, **48**, 508) accumulated new data in support of his earlier interpretation. The mechanism of oxidation has lately been studied by Afanasiev (*J. Phys. Chem. Russ.*, 1937, **9**, 559) who has emphasised the specificity of the action of Fe^{++} ions.

The present investigation is concerned with the clarification of the reaction mechanism from magnetic standpoint.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The purity of the substances employed was of a very high order. B. D. H. analytical reagents were purified and qualitatively and quantitatively analysed before use.

In the case of solutions, susceptibility has been calculated with the help of the reaction :

$$\chi_{\text{soln}} = \chi_{\text{salt}} \times C_{\text{salt}} + \chi_{\text{solvent}} (1 - C_{\text{salt}}).$$

Specific susceptibilities of the solutions of the same order of strength as were to be used in the reaction, were also determined and this relation-ship found to be valid.

The following solutions were prepared in conductivity water of which the susceptibility had been previously determined :

- (a) 0.10N-Potassium iodide.
- (b) 0.05N-Potassium persulphate
- (c) 1.00% Ferrous sulphate.

The solutions were placed in a constant temperature bath at 20°. After they had attained the temperature of the bath, 100 c.c. each of the iodide and persulphate solutions were pipetted out in a dry glass-stoppered flask and immediately shaken. Initial time was taken and the progress of the reaction followed by a chemical and magnetic analysis of the mixture at different intervals of time. The chemical composition was determined by withdrawing a known volume of the mixture, arresting the reaction in ice and immediately titrating the iodine set free against standard thiosulphate. The composition of the mixture with respect to its other ingredients can easily be evaluated from the thiosulphate consumption, since the latter is an accurate measure of the iodine content.

The specific susceptibilities of the reaction mixture were measured at different intervals and knowing the composition by a reference to the graph (time—thiosulphate), the values calculated theoretically on the mixture law were compared with the experimental values. These results are embodied in Tables IA and IB.

The reaction was next studied under exactly identical conditions in the presence of the catalyst. In this case 99.0 c.c. of 0.101N-potassium iodide were first measured out in the flask, 1 c.c. of the catalyst solution added and 100 c.c. of 0.05 N-persulphate mixed last of all. The reaction mixture was analysed chemically at different stages as above and its susceptibility determined on the Gouy's balance. The results of these measurements are embodied in Tables II A and II B.

The theoretical values of χ were calculated on the following data.

Compound.	$-\chi \times 10^6$.	Compound.	$-\chi \times 10^6$.
Iodine	+ 0.36	K ₂ SO ₄	+ 0.403
K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	+ 0.371	KI	+ 0.422
		FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	- 41.5

Reaction without catalyst.

TABLE IA.

Chemical analysis.

Vol. of the mixture solution used for titration = 10 c.c. Strength of thiosulphate = $N/51.75$. Temperature = 20° . V denotes volume of thio.

Reading.	Time.	V.	Reading.	Time.	V.
1	4 min.	0.40 c.c.	9	180 min.	7.70 c.c.
2	26	2.15	10	235	8.45
3	50	3.65	11	275	8.85
4	66	4.50	12	310	9.10
5	82	5.10	13	345	9.25
6	102	5.85	14	306	9.45
7	125	6.55	15	460	9.60
8	155	7.25			

TABLE IB.

Magnetic analysis.

d_4^{20} of the solution = 1.009. χ of water = -0.730×10^{-6} .

Reading.	Time.	Thio used.	Percentage composition.				$-\chi \times 10^6$	
			KI.	$K_2S_2O_8$.	K_2SO_4 .	I_2 .	Expt.	Calc.
1	23 min.	2.10 c.c.	0.7627	0.2830	0.0707	0.0515	0.726	0.726
2	46	3.60	0.7147	0.2439	0.1212	0.0883	0.726	0.726
3	62	4.46	0.6871	0.2214	0.1502	0.1094	0.727	0.726
4	78	5.05	0.6681	0.2059	0.1701	0.1239	0.727	0.726
5	100	5.80	0.6440	0.1864	0.1954	0.1423	0.727	0.726
6	122	6.50	0.6216	0.1681	0.2189	0.1594	0.727	0.726
7	150	7.20	0.5991	0.1498	0.2425	0.1766	0.727	0.726
8	177	7.65	0.5846	0.1380	0.2577	0.1877	0.727	0.726
9	247	8.55	0.5558	0.1145	0.2879	0.2097	0.727	0.726
10	270	8.82	0.5470	0.1074	0.2972	0.2164	0.727	0.726
11	303	9.04	0.5400	0.1017	0.3045	0.2218	0.727	0.726
12	340	9.22	0.5342	0.0970	0.3106	0.2262	0.727	0.726
13	408	9.46	0.5265	0.0907	0.3187	0.2321	0.728	0.726
14	456	9.60	0.5221	0.0871	0.3233	0.2355	0.728	0.726

Reaction with catalyst.

TABLE IIA.

Chemical analysis.

Reading.	Time.	Vol. of $N/51.50$ thiosulphate	Reading.	Time.	Vol. of $N/51.50$ thiosulphate.
1	5 min.	0.95 c.c.	7	95 min.	7.35 c.c.
2	15	2.25	8	112	7.95
3	27	3.50	9	126	8.30
4	46	4.90	10	166	9.10
5	62	5.95	11	204	9.65
6	76	6.60	12	6 hrs.	11.00

TABLE IIB.

Magnetic analysis.

d_4^{20} of the solution = 1.009. χ of water = -0.730×10^{-6} .

Reading.	Time.	Thio used.	Percentage composition.					$-\chi \times 10^6$.	
			KI.	$K_2S_2O_8$.	K_2SO_4 .	I_2 .	$FeSO_4$, $7H_2O$.	Expt.	Calc.
1	12 min.	2.00 c.c.	0.7656	0.2854	0.0677	0.0493	0.0005	0.724	0.724
2	25	3.00	0.7334	0.2592	0.1015	0.0730	0.0005	0.727	0.724
3	44	4.80	0.6754	0.2119	0.1625	0.1183	0.0005	0.730	0.724
4	60	5.80	0.6431	0.1856	0.1963	0.1430	0.0005	0.733	0.724
5	75	6.54	0.6193	0.1662	0.2213	0.1612	0.0005	0.730	0.724
6	92	7.30	0.5948	0.1463	0.2471	0.1799	0.0005	0.728	0.724
7	110	7.90	0.5754	0.1305	0.2674	0.1947	0.0005	0.726	0.724
8	126	8.30	0.5625	0.1200	0.2809	0.2046	0.0005	0.724	0.724
9	166	9.10	0.5367	0.0990	0.3080	0.2243	0.0005	0.723	0.724
10	200	9.60	0.5206	0.0859	0.3248	0.2366	0.0005	0.723	0.724
11	6 hr.	11.00	0.4754	0.0491	0.3724	0.2712	0.0005	0.723	0.724

DISCUSSION.

It is clear from Table IB that in the case of uncatalysed reaction, the observed susceptibilities follow, more or less, the additivity rule for a mixture. This shows that the formation of the iodide-iodine complex, KI_3 ,

in the reaction may have only a slight influence on the susceptibility (cf. Bhatnagar, Kapur and Varma, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1934, 9, 131; Ranganadham, *ibid.*, 1931, 6, 421).

In case of the catalysed reaction, the magnetic data (Table II B) reveal that

(a) at the initial stage, the mixture law is obeyed ;

(b) at intermediate stages, there is a marked divergence from it and the trend of values is towards greater diamagnetism ;

(c) at the final stages, divergence is but slight. This clearly indicates the formation of a relatively stable intermediary which is responsible for the accelerated velocity of the reaction. If iodine is liberated merely *via* ferric sulphate, as has been suggested by Kiss and Zombory (*loc. cit.*), the susceptibility of the resulting solutions ought to have remained more or less unchanged or at any rate the trend of values should have been towards lesser diamagnetism. (The ionic susceptibilities for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , calculated from the observed values for FeSO_4 and $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ are $\chi_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} = 11237 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\chi_{\text{Fe}^{3+}} = 11405 \times 10^{-6}$).

This is contrary to observations and hence it appears that the reaction mechanism involves the formation of a relatively stable diamagnetic or feebly paramagnetic complex, but it is abundantly clear that the mere formation of ferric sulphate cannot wholly account for the accelerated reaction velocity. The reaction mechanism may possibly entail the formation of a six-fold complex co-ordination compound of ferrous ion, since such a compound will have zero magnetic moment (Bose, *Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 5, 1048; Welo and Baudisch, *Nature*, 1925, 116, 606), as for example in the case of potassium ferrocyanide. Though it is not possible to say purely from magnetic considerations as to what compound is actually developed in the reaction, yet the importance of this method lies in the fact that it throws doubt on the earlier concepts of the mechanism of this reaction and indicates the direction in which to look for a proper interpretation for which further work is in hand.